

Enabling X-Ray Flux Integration for Improved Storm-Time Electron Density Predictions with Recurrent Neural Networks

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Current ionosphere models struggle during storm-time activity. We have developed a Machine Learning (ML) model of the electron density of the ionosphere that aims to improve upon existing approaches by incorporating Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) that also allow us to use X-ray flux data. We have trained three models on GPS Radio Occultation (GPSRO) data, which serve as stepping stone comparisons to highlight the advantages of RNNs and X-ray data incorporation. We compare these models with each other as well as with IRI and show improved performance, particularly during storm-time ($Kp * 10 \geq 50$). We see Pearson correlation coefficients for both hmf2 and nmf2 across the range of Kp values from 50 to 90 are higher across the board for the X-ray RNN approach, with a less pronounced difference during quiet-day conditions. This highlights the importance of using X-ray data to predict electron density of the ionosphere during storm-time. During quiet-day conditions, we see improved predictions when using RNNs.

1 Introduction

The ionosphere has important impacts on both ground and space assets. It is strongly coupled with space weather and directly affects wireless communications [1], especially satellite communications. Because of this coupling, it is desirable to have a model able to produce ionosphere predictions using space weather observations. Such a model would be valuable for many military and civilian applications, including GPS positioning [2, 3], synthetic aperture radar [4, 5], and the operation of most earth orbiting or space-based assets. The space weather impact on the ionosphere, particularly the presence of solar and geomagnetic storms, has a direct infrastructure impact, including impacts on power grids [6, 7], electrical devices [6], and health [6, 8, 9]. The electron density as a function of location is a good indicator of the state of the ionosphere. Although this is measurable, it is impossible to measure it everywhere, and is currently difficult to forecast.

There are four main ways in which the electron density is measured. These include (1) GPS Radio Occultation (GPSRO), which measures ionosphere properties by analyzing repeated signal paths sent between a GPSRO satellite and GPS satellite, (2) ionosondes, which work by sending signals of varying frequencies from the ground upward into the ionosphere and measuring reflection times, (3) Incoherent Scattering Radar (ISR) [10], which looks at the intensity of a return signal of a radar beam scattering off of electrons, and (4) in-situ measurement, where electron density is measured by an orbiting satellite (e.g., with a Langmuir probe). The first two measurements generally yield much more data (a path of measurements versus a single location), and thus have been more heavily leveraged in empirical (and more recently, Machine Learning (ML)) modeling of the ionosphere.

Additionally, there are many correlated or related measurements we can take of the Earth-Sun system. Many models use indices, which represent magnetic activity, and other common measurements.

1.1 Existing Approaches

Modeling the ionosphere is done in one of two main ways, either with closed-form physics-based modeling [11–14] or empirical-based modeling [15, 16], with both having advantages and drawbacks.

Physics-based models use known laws of physics to compute various values, but need functions that are defined everywhere to predict specific outputs (i.e., they can only use observations that are directly modeled). For example, one well-known physics-based ionospheric model called SAMI3 [12] cannot leverage the Interplanetary Magnetic Field (IMF), even though the IMF is understood to have a major impact on the ionosphere, particularly at the poles. Despite this, they can produce sensible and self-consistent results.

On the other hand, empirical models can be adjusted to incorporate additional factors, but are not necessarily restrained by physical requirements. Instead, empirical-based models are based on observa-

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tions. Although grounded in real measurements, extrapolation beyond the scope of past observations may not be reliable. A prominent example of an empirical model is the International Reference Ionosphere (IRI) [15, 17], which is widely used in the field. The IRI is steadily being improved upon and performs well under quiet-day conditions. It seems to struggle during storm-time as well as near the poles, as indicated by the creation of the E-CHAIM model [16], which focuses on higher latitude predictions.

Recently, a different empirical approach has arisen, based off of ML [18–25]. ML models have shown promising results when predicting electron density and appear to often outperform standard and widely-used empirical models, even when trained on a fraction of available data. Current machine learning models also predict much faster than most other approaches. While existing ML approaches perform well, they do not take much advantage of more recent advancements in the field of ML which move well beyond shallow feed-forward networks.

2 Methodology

2.1 Data

Our approach uses GPSRO data from multiple different sources spanning a range of over 20 years. We use the GPSRO data from the CHAMP [26] and GRACE [27] satellites and the COSMIC 1 [28] and COSMIC 2 [29] satellite constellations. Overall, this data spans approximately 100-600 km altitudes.

From these data sources, we use electron density profile measurements to create training, validation, and test data sets. Data is pre-processed to reject profiles with peak electron density outside of the 200-450 km altitude range with negative electron densities above 100 km (sub-100km negative densities are instead ignored), an approach introduced by [22] to reject poor-quality samples.

We split data into training, validation, and test sets temporally so training data is less correlated with validation and test sets. Training data is from 11-Jun-2001 through 31-Dec-2020. Validation data is all of 2021, and testing data is 2022 until 5-Oct-2022.

For supplemental input data, we use various indices from NASA's OMNI hourly data [30]. Currently, this is Dst, Kp, and, f10.7, but could easily be expanded with minor adjustments. We also use GOES X-ray data as input data [31], using all available satellites at the time of measurement and averaging satellites together when multiple were available.

2.2 Neural Network Architecture

We have developed a ML model for predicting electron density in the ionosphere. We base our model on a deeper architecture of existing approaches and augmented with standard RNNs [32]. It is composed of some input adjustments (e.g., sin and cos of $\frac{2\pi t}{24}$, where t is the UT hour) followed by 8 linear layers (compared to 2-4 of existing models). We combine non-temporal inputs with outputs of our recurrent section before passing it through the feed-forward part. We call this model Recurrent Deeper Ionosphere Neural Network (RDINN).

For comparison to existing approaches, we have a similar model without the recurrent section that we call Deeper Ionosphere Neural Network (DINN). The DINN model serves as a more direct comparison to existing ML approaches. It differs from existing approaches in two main ways, by being deeper (i.e., there are more hidden layers) with larger layers, and by being trained using a time-grouped batching approach.

Model inputs are latitude, longitude, altitude, year, day of year, hour, Kp index, ap index, Dst index, and solar index f10.7. The inputs are adjusted before being used in the feed forward layers as follows: the latitude is scaled between -1 and 1, the longitude is turned into a sine/cosine pair of values. Altitude is scaled to be in megameters. The year is simply used to determine if there is a leap year so that the day of year can be turned into a sine/cosine pair. The hour of the day is also converted into a sine/cosine pair. The Kp index is divided by 10, the Dst and ap indices are divided by 20 and the f10.7 index is divided by 150. The historical index values are not scaled. We use the past 72 hours of observations (taken every hour) for all four indices, as well the past 81 days of daily-averaged f10.7 data. The model outputs the log of electron density.

We use the recurrent architecture of the RDINN model to add X-ray flux measurements as inputs. We use both the short and long wavelengths at 1-minute averages for the past 90 minutes. We show the architecture of RDINN with X-ray data in Figure 1. In this architecture, the concatenate sections are what differentiate DINN, RDINN, and RDINN with X-ray. The DINN model excludes everything that is passed to the top part of the last concatenation (it has no RNNs), and the RDINN without X-ray does not use the X-ray portion in the first concatenation.

The DINN architecture has an input layer size of 12 (higher when used with RDINN), with hidden layers of sizes 64, 128, 128, 256, 128, 128, and 64, and an output layer of size 1. The feedforward layers use Sigmoid activation functions.

For the RDINN architecture, each RNN section has a hidden size of 64 with 3 layers. These are followed

Figure 1: RDINN XRS architecture, which appends X-ray RNNs to RDINN.

by a feedforward layer with an input size equal to 64 times the number of types of histories. This layer ends with a size of 16 and is concatenated into the input to the DINN architecture (so the DINN part of RDINN has an input size of 28).

For our models we use Mean Squared Error (MSE) on the log of electron density as our loss function. We train for a total of 100 epochs using a time-grouped batching approach and select the model where validation loss stops decreasing as the trained model. A time-grouped batching approach is used to improve model inter-consistency as each batch has a set of correlated samples that are close temporally, forcing the model to fit to multiple spatial locations at similar times to hopefully improve global prediction performance. We use a batch size of 16384 data points. After preprocessing the data, training takes about 1.1 days for DINN, 9.8 days for RDINN, and 16 days for RDINN with XRS on an RTX 3090. Of important note is that because GOES XRS data is not always present, the X-ray version of RDINN has seen fewer total samples per epoch (1.28 billion vs 1.36 billion).

3 Results

3.1 General Performance

Our model performance can be characterized by comparing predictions against electron density measurements in the GPSRO test described earlier. We produce correlation plots in Figure 2, where we plot the 185M test points for model predictions (vertical) against the observed values (horizontal). We also report the Pearson correlation coefficient (R). In this case, the closer the R value is to 1 the closer the model-truth correspondence is to the dashed red line.

From this we can see that both two types of models, DINN and RDINN, outperform IRI. Additionally, RDINN, with recurrent information, performs slightly better than the model without. The impacts from

Figure 2: Correlation plots of predictions vs GPSRO testing data, with 185M test points. The ideal is represented as a straight line. Data below 100km is omitted the D region modeling is a separate task not suited to the models and datasets used. Yellow data indicates concentrations above the colorbar limit.

changes in the Earth-Sun system are not instantaneous, and having a history of them, captured in the recurrent layers, improves the problem context.

Curiously, we see a slight decrease in performance for RDINN with X-ray compared to RDINN, which may be because of the smaller amount of training data. It is important to note here that test data is GPSRO data like the training data, but a similar trend between models and IRI was noticed on other sets of data as well (such as ISR data at Jicamarca).

3.2 Storm-Time Results

Although adding X-rays to the recurrent model did not result in an overall improvement, during storm-time conditions, we find a significant advantage to including X-ray flux data. Figure 3 shows model results on ionosonde measurements of hmf2 and nmf2.

Figure 3: Correlation plots of the predictions against ionosonde measurements of hmf2, with 400k test points.

Figure 4: Correlation plots of the predictions against ionosonde measurements of nmf2, with 400k test points.

We filter the data so that all measurements are during storm-time with Kp values of at least 5. These ionosonde measurements span between 1987 and 2023 and approximately 100 locations [33].

Using the same comparative approach, we show storm-time predictions in Figures 3 and 4. We omit IRI results in this section because IRI is trained on ionosonde data, some of which is included in this test set. Notably, although omitted, we did run this for the IRI and found better performance from our own models for the metrics presented.

From Figures 3 and 4, we can see that the X-ray version of the model performs the best, followed by the recurrent version and then the non-recurrent version. This trend continues if we break down the correlation coefficient metric for different ranges of Kp values, which we do in Figure 5.

When looking along these Kp values, we notice that the X-ray recurrent model has the highest correlation coefficients for all cases. Additionally, for nmf2, the recurrent model, RDINN, outperforms the non-recurrent DINN. For hmf2, the RDINN and DINN models go back and forth on which is outperforming the other.

We see similar results if we consider mean squared error or mean absolute error instead, as in Figures 6 and 7.

For model prediction error on hmf2 and nmf2, at high Kp , the X-ray approach has the lowest error, except in some lower Kp ranges where errors are very close. Similarly, RDINN has lower error than DINN in most cases.

From this, it can be gathered that the introduction of the recurrent model, which uses the historical information on top of what is given to DINN, performs

Figure 5: Correlation of the predictions against ionosonde measurements along Kp ranges. Higher is better.

Figure 6: Mean squared error of the predictions against ionosonde measurements along Kp ranges. Lower is better.

slightly better during storm-time conditions (as well as quiet-day conditions) even without introducing X-ray data. Notably, the introduction of X-ray data significantly increases the accuracy of model predictions, especially in the high Kp ranges above 75.

4 Discussion

We have demonstrated three main things in this paper that we wish to explicitly highlight. First, as demonstrated in previous papers, ML models can be used to reasonably predict ionosphere electron density. Second, adding recurrent architecture and incorporating historical data lends better performance. Third, this recurrent architecture allows us to effectively use other types of data that are important in ionosphere modeling, specifically X-ray flux measurements, and that this inclusion seems to bolster performance during storm-time conditions.

As DINN is comparable to existing ML approaches, we believe that RDINN outperforms them or their capabilities given similar training sets as RDINN out-

Figure 7: Mean absolute error of the predictions against ionosonde measurements along Kp ranges. Lower is better.

performs DINN (especially with the addition of X-ray flux data). Thus, with an analogous adjustment, existing ML models could be improved as well.

In future work we aim to incorporate larger sets of training data, including ionosonde data and ISR data. We also wish to investigate scaling our MSE error with the log of electron density so that the objective function scales better at low electron density locations.

While we could adjust the DINN architecture to use X-ray and historical data as well, using recurrent architectures on structured temporal data has been shown to increase performance [34, 35]. Additionally, we chose this set of 3 models to address two goals: to demonstrate the usefulness of recurrent architecture in ionosphere modeling, and to demonstrate the importance of using X-ray data in ionosphere modeling, which is done by comparing DINN and RDINN for the former and RDINN and RDINN with X-ray for the latter. We also admit that further improvements could be made using different types of recurrent architectures, which we aim to explore in future work, including using transformer networks instead.

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